

Agro2Circular

D7.4 – Community based innovation schemes

July 2025

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List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
ATC	Alhama Town Council
AoTA	Associations of traders in Alhama
AoTRM	Associations of street traders in the Region of Murcia
CARM	Autonomous Community of Region of Murcia
CBS	Community-Based Scheme
CDS	Communication and Dissemination Strategy
CEBM	Circular Economy Business Models
DoA	Description of the Action
Dn.n	Deliverable (number)
DIS	Data Integration System
F2F	Face to face
IAP2	International Association of Public Participation
KPIs	Key performance indicators
LTtA	Lorca and Totana street trader association
Tn.n	Task (number)
WPn	Work Package (number)

Glossary

Community based schemes: plans designed to engage and mobilise the community's resources for the benefit of its members. In this context, the concept of community refers to “a group living in a specific geographical or administrative area, for example, a neighbourhood, which has access to and uses the same service” [1], [2].

Description of the Action: In an H2020 project, the DoA is a document that sets out the envisaged solution, including the project work plan and information regarding the scope, cost, timeframe and risks of the project, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables and the project organisation and approach.

Face-to-face infrastructure: In the context of public participation processes, face-to-face participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room) or virtually through teleconferences to enable citizen engagement at all levels.

Public engagement: It is understood as the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of research can be shared with the public. Engagement is a two-way process involving interaction and listening aimed at generating mutual benefit at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower). The concept is considered a synonym for public participation and/or citizen engagement and both terms will be used throughout the document.

Virtual infrastructures: In the context of public participation processes, virtual infrastructures comprise of online platforms, application software and collaborative channels that assist purposeful citizen engagement at all levels within a given territory (municipality, region, country, EU).

1 Executive summary <abstract>

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.4. *Community based innovation schemes* and is a summary of activities and results of the Agro2Circular project undertaken within task 7.1.2 *Community-based innovation schemes*, detailing the activities implemented and the lessons learnt, to be applied at regional level and with potential replicability in other European Regions. Deliverable D7.16 Reports on potential for adoption and scale-up of the A2C solutions and deliverables D7.17 and D7.18 explain the action plan for replication in regions, namely Lombardy and Lithuania respectively. given that both countries have, among many other common factors, the existence of local markets with similar characteristics to the one in which the activity has been carried out.

The first part of the deliverable summarizes the results and lessons learnt during the implementation of a community-based innovation pilot action, carried out by FUNDACION PRIMAFRIO at the local town market in Alhama de Murcia, to promote circular social practices among citizens and to raise awareness of the A2C project and food waste. This action consisted of

- 1- Organisational activities such as meetings and logistical tasks prior to the implementation of the community-based innovation scheme,
- 2- Installing bins at local food markets in Alhama de Murcia, encouraging vendors to deposit fruit and vegetable waste. The waste collected was then incorporated into the project's value chain for recovery.
- 3-Information stands were set up at the entrance of the market to inform citizens about recycling and circular economy practices and the technologies and products developed in the framework of the Agro2Circular project.
- 4-Raffles to attract and involve the market visitors in activities aimed at spreading knowledge on circular economy
- 5-Interviews and surveys to evaluate the social impact.

These activities were performed during two years, the first year we evaluated the challenges found during the implementation and the lessons learnt from the experience engaging market vendors and the public. After the first year of the activity, a summer pause provided the opportunity to reflect on the changes that would be required in the second year, The second part of the deliverable collects 16 community-based schemes gathered by KVC, UVEG, LPK and TCA in 5 different EU countries (Italy, UK, Chile, Spain and Lithuania), summarizing key features such as the participants, methodologies, results and impacts. Finally, general conclusions are provided in section 6 and the Annex, to be considered in future initiatives includes the materials (Flyers, posters, and rollups) designed to inform the public on during the community-based scheme implemented in Alhama de Murcia.

2 Introduction

The European Union is working hard to devise a plan for the transition to a more sustainable economy to combat the environmental challenges facing humanity. This plan is outlined in the European Green Deal[3], which among other things promotes the adoption of the circular economy. To achieve these objectives, it is necessary to raise awareness and involve citizens as indispensable actors to achieve this transition.

Agro2Circular project aims to implement a circular territorial solution for the upcycling of agrifood waste generated in the Region of Murcia. In addition to the development of the technology necessary for the valorisation of this type of waste, another A2C important objective is to contribute to citizens' awareness of the need for a more sustainable economy based on reduce, recycling, reuse and circular practices. To boost public engagement, Agro2Circular project included a specific task (Community-based innovation Schemes) within work package 7 (A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability) with the objective of implementing a pilot community-based innovation action for public engagement to raise awareness and promote circular social practices with the participation of the municipality and local stakeholders. Community-based schemes have arisen worldwide as a strategy for waste management, reducing the amount of waste entering landfills and therefore, pollution and carbon emissions, while improving people's economic welfare through job creation [1], [2], [4]. Furthermore, community based schemes can address other topics, such as sustainable land management [5] or health insurance issues [6]. A common feature of many of these schemes is that they aim to fulfil a gap, specifically the collection and recovery of waste in contexts where conventional collection (through waste management services) is not available. In some cases, this lack of management is a result of physical conditions hampering access, logistical barriers, or socio-cultural contexts (lack of awareness of skills, insufficient resources including funding, lack of involvement in community issues)[7], [8].

Therefore, it is also important to identify and evaluate what schemes have been developed in other regions as successful examples to be considered fostering public participation in circular economy initiatives/projects.

3 . Community engagement in Alhama

3.1 Preparation

The activity developed in the weekly market of Alhama, started with an informative meeting with the Town Council of Alhama and different councillors who could be linked to the project (Education, Local Development, Responsible of the Training and Employment Centre and Local Development).

Figure 1. List of meetings between the entities involved in the project

In these previous sessions, information was given on the following topics:

- The Agro2circular project
- The initiatives that are taking place in Alhama de Murcia, both the video game contests on circular economy and the activities programmed in the Tuesday street market with the selective collection of food waste for subsequent transfer to the partner in charge of its valorization, in this case CTNC.
- Comment on the location of the collaborating stalls (selling fruits and vegetables) and the bins to deposit fruit and vegetable waste.
- Comments on the location of informative stalls

Subsequently, in the Training and Employment Centre for Local Development, meetings were held to frame the A2C project in the activity of the Street Market with the presence of representatives of CETEC and the Market Associations, and Street Traders of the Region of Murcia, to make them aware of the pilot experience, informing them of the need for their participation and gathering suggestions and comments to the initiative (Figure 2).

They were very receptive to contribute to the implementation of the project, requesting information about the project in Spanish and posters to reflect their collaboration in the European project.

Hence the need for leaflets, posters, roll up, tent logos (Figure 27, Figure 28 , Figure 29 and Figure 30 in Annex).

Figure 2. Meeting with representatives of Alhama de Murcia City Hall and market vendors

It was agreed that 6 small containers would be available, 120 L, one for each type of waste (broccoli, cauliflower, apple, lemon, grape, artichoke). These stalls would be concentrated in two streets and the City Council suggested a location for the containers to which the vendors would take the waste every day. PRIMAFRIO would take the containers each day and collect them at the end of the day to send them to CTNC.

3.2 First year of the Activity

3.2.1 Description of activities

22/11/22 First day, visit partners, Majors, town hall. Inauguration of the activity.

The activity started (figure 3) by inviting the technology centres, partners in its inauguration, setting up a tent with the logos of the regional entities and the containers collecting the waste deposited in them for the purposes of the project.

The selective collection activities are subsequently combined with training, dissemination and workshops linked to the circular economy.

The attendees at this opening day included the City Council, Kveloce, CNTC, Eversia, Cetec, and the media were invited to publicise the activity.

Early in the morning, the boxes of bags that Eversia had provided, with the leaflet and poster requested by the Merchants, had been handed out, indicating the location of the containers, agreeing to remove the waste that was collected at the end of the day.

After the press conference, a visit was made, together with the Majors, to the market, talking to the sellers and visitors, inviting them to collaborate. News were published at [Infolínea.es broadcasting](https://www.infolinea.es) (Cover story and page 2, Figure 3), and the [Alhama de Murcia City Council news section of the website](#) (Figure 4), [Major's Mariola Guevara social networks](#) (Figure 5) , [local digital media 7Dias Alhama](#) (Figure 6) and [Conecta Magazine Digital press](#) (Figure 7). In addition, television and radio, media such as Telealhama and Cope Espuña broadcasted the event.

At the end of the day, when the number of visitors had decreased, 2 bags of fruit and vegetables were collected and taken to the CNTC.

2 INFORMACIÓN GENERAL Nº 1.270 - 25 de noviembre de 2022

Se pone en valor la revalorización de los residuos alimenticios, contribuyendo de esta forma al fomento de una economía circular

El Ayuntamiento, Fundación Primafrio, CETEC, CTNC, KVELOCE y EVERSIA se suman al Proyecto Europeo Agro2Circular

Los comerciantes de frutas y verduras recibieron una caja con lo necesario para recoger los residuos y depositarlos en los contenedores

En respuesta a su compromiso con la sostenibilidad, Fundación Primafrio, CETEC, CTNC, Ayuntamiento de Alhama, KVELOCE y EVERSIA colaboran en la recogida selectiva de residuos hortofrutícolas procedentes del Mercadillo de Alhama de Murcia para su posterior investigación en el Proyecto Europeo Agro2Circular.

El Proyecto Agro2Circular tiene como objetivo demostrar la viabilidad de la economía circular en los residuos más representativos del sector agroalimentario en la Región de Murcia, esto es, en los restos de frutas y hortalizas, y en los plásticos multicapa.

Estos residuos serán seleccionados a partir del excedente de determinados alimentos y, posteriormente, serán enviados al Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva (CTNC). En este centro especializado se procederá a su posible incorporación en la producción de ingredientes

Representantes y entidades colaboradoras en el proyecto

destinados a fórmulas nutricionales, cosméticos, alimentos u otros productos de alto valor añadido.

El mercado semanal de Alhama acogió el pasado martes 22 de noviembre la primera recogida selectiva de diversos residuos hortofrutícolas, dentro de este proyecto.

Los residuos hortofrutícolas aptos son coliflor, brócoli, alcachofas, manzanas, uvas y limones, los cuales se podrán depositar y reciclar en unos contenedores especiales del mercado local de Alhama durante varios días, de los meses entre noviembre de 2022 a octubre de 2023.

Estos productos tendrán como destino el Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva, donde servirán de fuente para este proyecto. Unido a la recogida selectiva programada, se desarrollarán diferentes campañas de sensibilización medioambiental y jornadas divulgativas relacionadas con la economía circular y vinculadas a estos pro-

ductos generados, destinadas a fomentar la participación ciudadana.

El Centro Tecnológico del Calzado participa en el desarrollo tecnológico de la cadena del valor de los residuos plásticos, para poder obtener un producto y volver a ser utilizado como envase o en la agricultura. También desarrollan la producción de plásticos biodegradables a partir de los residuos de alimentación.

En esta iniciativa pionera participan más de 40 empresas a nivel europeo, 16 de ellas de la Región de Murcia, para dar viabilidad a la economía circular a través del reciclaje, en residuos que se generan por ejemplo a través de este mercado, como frutas y verduras. "Es dar una segunda vida a esos residuos", explica la alcaldesa Mariola Guevara.

El enfoque A2C se prueba en la Región de Murcia (Espa-

Contenedores ubicados en la zona

ña) y se replicará en otros dos países de la UE (Italia y Lituania), respaldado por un modelo de negocio circular y fuertes procesos de participación pública y co-creación, maximizando su réplica y escalado.

Esto permitirá reducir la huella ambiental, crear puestos de trabajo, adoptar un modelo más eficiente y sostenible de gestión de los recursos y la implicación de una sociedad participativa que ayude a su generación.

En palabras de Juan Conesa, presidente de Fundación Primafrio, "formar parte de este proyecto internacional nos da la oportunidad de valorizar residuos cotidianos que son muy frecuentes en nuestra Región de Murcia y que pueden aportar mucho a la economía circular".

Toni López

Figure 3 Newspaper clipping of the inauguration of the street market in Alhama

Figure 4. News section of Alhama de Murcia website

Figure 5. Social Media of Alhama's Major Mariola Guevara

INICIO SUSCRIPCIÓN AL BOLETÍN CONTACTO

7 Días alhama

siete

POLÍTICA SUCESOS EMPRESAS EDUCACIÓN DEPORTES CULTURA SOCIEDAD MEDIO AMBIENTE AGRICULTURA PEDANÍAS
ECONOMÍA SANIDAD RELIGIÓN TRIBUNALES LIBRILLA COLABORACIONES

V/F Alhama, pionera en un proyecto de economía circular

'Agro2circular' se ha puesto en marcha en el mercado de los martes para dar una segunda vida a los residuos plásticos y alimentarios

Figure 6. News in digital press 7Dias Alhama

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Figure 7. News in the digital press Conecta Magazine

13/12/22 Day with AGROFOOD and AGROTRANSFORMADOS (MCT), delivery of products related to the project.

The project presented products from the project partners; bags, juices, jams, and merchandising with messages. (Figure 8)

At the beginning, the regulars of the weekly market in Alhama were a bit reluctant to come to the booth, but thanks to these products, they started to ask about and take an interest in the project and to share their experiences on the subject.

The assessment of the people with whom we were able to interact was generally positive, encouraging us to develop more far-reaching initiatives, although we also met people who were more sceptical about the impact of the project, in relation to the magnitude of the problem.

We returned, together with the Local Development technician, to talk to the sellers reminding them of the waste collection initiative (Figure 9). There are about 32 stalls that participate in this initiative, almost all of the fruit and vegetable stalls, those who did not collaborate was because they do not sold the products selected in the project or because the collection had been scarce, as according to CNTC specifications, a minimum number of kilos was necessary for evaluation.

Those who do not collaborate were because they do not sell the products selected in the project. However, the collection has been scarce, only of cauliflower, which according to CNTC specifications, would have to provide a minimum amount (kg) for evaluation.

Figure 8. Delivery of samples of Agrotransformados products at the Alhama market

Figure 9. Containers for the selective collection of fruit and vegetables at the Alhama market

07/02/23 We start with the recycling activities

We started with the recycling dissemination and learning activity, with a test to raise awareness of the importance of separating waste correctly, and a practical activity at the same stand. Participants were given a fridge magnet as a gift.

The activity was well received and approximately 125 people took part.

The amount of waste collected in the specific containers, as well as the characteristics required for further treatment, were not the expected, only when reminded by the City Council technician and us is when they deposit some of the rest of the chosen products (cauliflower leaves), but they do not reach the kg. to be taken to the CNTC. In addition, there is a circular economy established practice between the stalls and their customers, as some of them have animals and/or organic vegetable gardens, and the distribution to these users is agreed upon. These activities took place, every two weeks, till June 2023.

18/04/23 Raffle and first survey

A raffle and a survey were also carried out to find out, during this first year, the knowledge of circular economy that has been imparted during this period, with success both in terms of participation and congratulations on the initiative. This town has an important community of foreigners, active in the field of sustainability and who have transmitted their predisposition to support initiatives in this direction.

Figure 10. Winner of the fruit basket among those surveyed at the Alhama street market

The raffle (Figure 10) consisted of a draw among those who took part in the survey for 20 kg of fruit purchased at the stalls collaborating in this initiative.

Taking advantage of the day, scenes of the market were filmed for the documentary that is being made about the project Agro2Circular (Figure 11).

El valor oculto del residuo - The Hidden Value of Waste

Figure 11. Videodocumentary

The number of visitors to this activity varies according to the time of year, especially due to inclement weather, with the busiest time being those that coincide with non-teaching dates, where grandparents are accompanied by grandchildren who participate in the recycling workshops and tourist visitors with the arrival of spring without reaching the high temperatures of summer.

3.2.2 Challenges and difficulties

The collection quantities demanded by CTNC were not reached because the market vendors already had their own circular schemes involving citizens visiting the market.

The market sellers indicate that not much waste is generated at the stalls because even poorer looking products are sold at a lower price for animal feeding.

We have had to do more workshops and interactive content to make people come every week to learn about the project and disseminate the principles of the circular economy, serving as a point for complaints and suggestions for improvement in their municipality, that is to say:

- About the dimensions and location of the containers for the deposit of waste.
- Queries about recycling different products, e.g. vapers.

3.2.3 Lessons learnt

The collection of the products selected in the project has not had the expected repercussions, not because of the predisposition of the sellers, whom we have periodically informed of this initiative, in various ways, accompanied by the local development technician. Rather, it was due to conflicting interests, i.e. they already have a commitment to their own customers who collect this type of waste either for animal farms or for composting.

Therefore, the source of obtaining this type of waste from these centres has traditionally had a circular solution, perhaps not the one with the greatest valorisation, but it implies an awareness and attitude that this project, we believe, has reinforced.

3.3 Second year of the activity

3.3.1 Description of activities

Given that the collection of products at the flea market is not having any success due to the arguments put forward above and there were few times when sufficient waste was collected for processing, it was decided to intensify the work of dissemination and data collection.

19/12/2023 The flea market activity resumes.

On this day many new people approached us and the project was explained to them and they found it very interesting, and people who knew us asked about the activities that we were going to carry out in order to participate.

The delivery of bags for use in the market was demonstrated to be very useful to passers-by at shopping time, so they first pass by our stall to collect them and see the activity of the day, as well as gradually differentiating the bags for their correct recycling.

16/01/24 Alliances with other entities.

An average of 300 people passed by, half of them already knew us, but the rest have told us that it is important to be there to raise awareness.

We were also visited by the Trade Technician, together with the Councillor for Trade, to coordinate with the company that manages the waste to make joint workshops in these months. Another visit was from the Poseidon Diving Club of Alhama, to promote this type of initiative with collections and awareness in schools.

25/06/24 last day of the season

This day was one of the busiest days, classes had finished, and the grandparents came with their grandchildren to participate in the different recycling activities, showing their elders the knowledge acquired at school, some also knew us from the talks held in their educational centre or the video game competition.

Another important group was the foreigners, who usually visit the market on holiday and happened to be interested in the project.

03/12/24 survey to evaluate the social impact

During this day two activities were carried out in parallel, together with the Kveloce team (Figure 12): on the one hand interviews with various market traders and on the other hand, a survey to the public using the market, handing out samples of plastic bags and cosmetics provided by the partners Eversia and Lolobio.

Figure 12. Interview and surveys on the impact of the activity at the Alhama street market

3.3.2 Challenges and difficulties

This year, we have focused on developing more activities to raise awareness and disseminate the Circular Economy, using the Agro2circular Project as an example. For this reason, the traders who are more familiar with our presence, once again this year, and without the dilemma of deciding where to deposit the little waste they can produce from the selected products, have shown even more collaboration by referring customers to our stall and by passing on the Project when they were asked about it.

The inclement weather, as in the first year, has sometimes made it impossible for us to set up our stall or make it necessary to reduce the working day.

At the end of the second year of the activity, it was planned to assess the social impact of the activity, but the extension of the project diffculted this evaluation. Hence, additional sessions had to be planned after summer 2024 to materialise this activity and to provide the opportunity of testing the products generated in the project

3.3.3 Lessons learned

As a result of the above, we have tried to focus the work of the market on raising awareness about food waste, the importance of local and seasonal consumption, the more responsible

use of plastics, recycling workshops and games, and dissemination of the project itself We were able to evaluate the results in surveys (initially carried out in a very positive way), which were aligned with our preliminary perception: that we have been effectively sending a message to promote changes through small gestures that commit us all.

We believe that the delivery of certain products provided by the partners has also contributed to bring the population closer to the project's objective, not only conceptual, but also acting as a stimulus for their consultation, interest and approach as a material experience of this action; highlighting the importance of constancy, novelty and proximity to the problem in order to link and maintain their interest.

4 Other community-based initiatives

4.1 Criteria for the selection of community-based schemes:

For the selection of community-based schemes, the following criteria were followed:

- 1) Link or contact to find further information is available.
- 2) The community-based scheme has shown evidence of positive or promising results to implement the Circular Economy:

Some examples of results are:

a) Awareness/capacity building. The community based scheme contributes to sensitize to the subject of circular economy. I.e:

- ✓ Offers clear definitions of the concept of Circular Economy and its relationship with climate change, biodiversity loss, and other environmental problems.
- ✓ The community based scheme program promotes the knowledge and skills for training/awareness raising about circular economy

b) Promotes empowerment:

- ✓ The community-based scheme provides skills and resources to promote participation in decision-making processes

c) Living environment approach:

- ✓ The community-based scheme takes into account differences related to culture, social background, people from vulnerable groups, etc.
- ✓ The community-based scheme addresses attitudes, behaviours and beliefs regarding the acceptance of circular economy services and products.

- 3) The community-based scheme includes tools/resources (data, methods and tools) to monitor and assess its impact or effectiveness.

Some examples of impacts are:

- ✓ The decrease of waste generation
- ✓ The increase in positive interactions among stakeholders in waste management
- ✓ The significant increase in knowledge, skills and awareness on waste management
- ✓ The design and/or adoption of effective governance models in circular economy (policy makers, industry, citizens).

- 4) The community-scheme is sustainable at the long term

Factors that indicate the sustainability at the long term are:

- ✓ The community-scheme is embedded within a broader action plan, circular economy strategy or related regulations.
- ✓ Has long-term funding to be repeated or maintained in the future.
- ✓ Has built cooperation agreements with different stakeholders.

- 5) The community-based scheme has an **innovative character**, or implies innovative aspects (e. g. actual knowledge, new ideas or methodology, etc).

What is a “social innovation”?

"A process, product or program that profoundly changes the way a given system operates, changing it in such a way that reduces the vulnerability of the people and the environment in that system. As a consequence of a positive social innovation, a system grows more resilient" (SiG, 2014).

- 6) The community-based scheme can be implemented at low cost
7) The community-based scheme can be transferred to other contexts

How can we assess transferability?

- ✓ Accesibility;
 - a) There is free access to the methodology and how the program has been implemented (e. g. process description, manual etc.); or
 - b) The access is subject to payment of material, program, fee or license are paid.
- ✓ The program has already been successfully transferred to another region.
- ✓ The program does not rely too much on specific aspects of the national/regional system.
- ✓ The program does not depend too much on one/few specific professional qualifications and/ or profiles.

4.2 Cascina Cuccagna

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Cascina Cuccagna		
Country/region	Italy (Milano)		
Promoter/initiator	CASCINA CUCCAGNA	Type of entity	NGO or CSO
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2022 -	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.milanoristorazione.it/progetti/progetti-in-corso/3193-insieme-a-siticibo-recuperiamo-le-eccedenze-e-diciamo-no-allo-spreco		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food (Food surplus)		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs, <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations		
Objectives:	Reduction of Food Waste and Redistribution: Recover surplus bread and unconsumed fruits from school cafeterias for redistribution to non-profit organizations and charitable structures in the area.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement of schools in the recovery of unconsumed bread and fruits. • Collaboration with the Association “Banco Alimentare della Lombardia – Siticibo”. • Distributed collection network across various schools. 		

Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction: Reducing food waste through recovery and redistribution. • Recovery: Recovering unconsumed bread and fruits. • Reuse: Reusing food for charitable purposes.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability balance: Link to pdf • Food bank: https://www.bancoalimentare.it/ • A recipe book with 23 recipes against Food waste was distributed (in Italian, under requirement in webpage).
Related costs	The only costs are related to logistics because volunteers are involved in food collection and distribution.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<i>Not required</i>
Impact and sustainability	In the 2022/23 school year, more than 50 schools were involved, collecting more than 17.100 kg of bread and almost 39.000 kg of uneaten fruit. For the 2023/24 school year, the joint aim is to intensify this network, in order to make the collection even more widespread, while also accepting requests from voluntary associations operating close to schools.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italy Good Samaritan Law Legge del Buon Samaritano (Law n 155, 2003) -16/07/2023). Access https://www.bancoalimentare.it/news/legge-del-buon-samaritano-dieci-anni-recuperate-oltre-2-milioni-di-porzioni-di-piatti-pronti • Legge Gadda (Law n°166, 14/09/2016) https://www.bancoalimentare.it/legge-gadda
Social innovation	Established initiative involving schools, third-sector entities, and volunteer associations. Promotes solidarity culture among citizens. Includes a change on how private business operate (restoration services in schools) recognising social value. Develops partnerships between private and third sector (food banks)
Challenges and barriers	<p>Legislative framework: Normative barriers removed in Italy by Good Samaritan Law, and Legge Gadda, may exist in other countries (i.e. Ireland has not a Good Samaritan Law),</p> <p>Network Expansion: Challenges in intensifying the network, logistical coordination, potential challenges related to awareness and participation from schools.</p>

4.3 Community Fridge Network

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Community Fridge Network		
Country/region	UK		
Promoter/initiator	HUBBUB	Type of entity	NGO or CSO
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2017-	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	Website: https://hubbub.org.uk/community-fridge-network Contact: hello@hubbub.org.uk		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food Waste prevention		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: producers, gardens		
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce food waste, by expanding the Community Fridge Network (CFN), helping groups create and launch their own community fridges across the UK. • Address food insecurity, by providing more communities with surplus food access to healthy food. • Building community cohesion, by supporting communities with valuable skills (such as cooking and gardening) and spaces for social connection 		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hubbub provides guidance, training and financial support, and sharing knowledge and experiences between community fridges. • Alliances: Major partners such as Co-op, The Rothschild Foundation, and Starbucks have supported this initiative, allowing an additional 50 groups to develop their own food hub activities.
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rethink: Encouraging individuals and businesses to rethink their approach to collaborative consumption within communities. • Redistribution: from local businesses and individuals, preventing it from being wasted and promoting its reuse within the community. • Reuse: In some cases, community fridges are set up using donated equipment, such as a fridge.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	Impact report 2024. Link to pdf. Impact Report 2022. Link to pdf
Related costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Costs: Electricity, Waste Management, Insurance, Printing, Pest Control, Transportation, etc. • Equipment and Maintenance Costs: setting up and maintaining the physical infrastructure of the community fridges, such as fridges, sheds, materials, contracting services, storage space, etc. • Staffing Costs: if volunteers cannot provide the level of management support required. • Training and Support Costs: associated with providing training and support to volunteers and staff members involved in running the community fridges. • Food Handling and Safety Costs: obtaining necessary certifications, implementing food hygiene practices, and conducting regular inspections.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<i>Not required</i>
Impact and sustainability	<p>Impact: figures in 2022 impact report. Decrease of food waste generation (181 fridges opened, 7129 tonnes estimated food shared); increase of positive interactions (50 new food hubs developed), access to food (16.9 million equivalent meals shared)</p> <p>Sustainability: Creating local networks for food, skills, and knowledge sharing, volunteer-driven models reduce operational costs; adaptable to changing needs.</p>
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate Sponsorship • Donations from individuals and organizations • Grants to network members to set up growing projects, a community food hub, a recipe box scheme and a refill pantry. • Volunteer Support, Fundraising and Grants: Community Fridges depend on these to cover costs.
Social innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activism: they encourage volunteers and community members to actively participate in addressing local challenges. • Knowledge transfer: they provide training and capacity building on different areas related to the project.
Challenges and barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness of the community fridge: may not be the most effective method for reducing waste at home. • Limited individual food donations and restrictions on acceptable items • Community Engagement: Maintaining community engagement and participation over time.

4.4 Imeko

Figure 13. Photo at Imeko website

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Imeko. Cigarette butt recycling		
Country/region	Chile		
Promoter/initiator	Imeko	Type of entity	Private/industry/business
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2018-	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	Website: https://imeko.cl/ Contact: https://imeko.cl/contactanos/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Collection and processing of cigarette butts (cellulose acetate) and its transformation into a new sustainable and recyclable material for industry		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs, <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: waste managers		
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To bring science and innovation together to tackle cigarette butt pollution. • To foster circular economy of cigarette butts, from its management to its recovery • To transform cigarette butts into a sustainable material for the future which can be used in conventional plastic moulding processes, while helping to clean up the planet. 		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	The intervention involves a subscription-based collection service for cigarette butts across Chile using branded containers (over 400 collection points nationwide). Cigarette butts are processed through sustainable chemical techniques to remove toxic substances and extract cellulose acetate to produce Celion®, a raw material sold to other businesses. Imeko also conducts environmental and anti-smoking education (social media, clean ups)
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rethink: providing education and awareness about the environmental impact of cigarette butt waste. • Recover: The initiative aims to recover valuable materials from cigarette butts, specifically cellulose acetate, through chemical techniques. • Recycle: Cigarette butts are collected, processed, and transformed into Celion®, a recyclable material for industry.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News from t13 Link • Pais circular news. Link
Related costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified costs: may entail human Resources/Staff, processing and Equipment Costs, and administrative and Marketing Costs
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste Separation/Classification: involves a subscription-based collection service for cigarette butts across Chile using branded containers. • Waste Management and Recovery: Technology to transform waste to produce new raw material for other uses.
Impact and sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental impact: 6.270.369 recycled butts, 698 kg CO₂eq saved: 23.765.445 L Unpolluted Water. For every kilo of recycled cigarette butt, 750 grams of plastic recovered and 2.7 kilos of CO₂ are no longer emitted. Social impact: raises awareness about environmental issues and promotes sustainable behaviours. Economic impact: creation of new markets for recycled materials and sustainable products. • Long-Term Sustainability: financially viable business model paves the way for scalability and replication actions in other regions or communities.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct grants: Imeko received funding from the Directorate of Innovation and Entrepreneurship from the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso (2018). Corfo's Huella programme (2021). • Investments: first investment round (2023) • Business model: Waste management services for companies (including restoration) and public administrations; selling Celion® as a raw material (used for sunglasses in Patagonia)
Social innovation	Activism (participation in clean-ups, installation of bins for cigarette butt disposal). Knowledge transfer: awareness-raising.
Challenges and barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste collection: requires disposal of the butt in specific containers and the reduction of cigarette littering. • Social behaviours and awareness: addictive nature of cigarettes, required campaigns to reduce cigarette littering, fostering responsible smoking habits • Technological: lack of recycling facilities, complexity of the recycling process • Economic barriers: low demand for recycled cellulose acetate products.

4.5 Talkual

Figure 14. Website shop

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Talkual. Naturally imperfect: Fruits and vegetables that are unique on the outside and awesome on the inside.		
Country/region	Spain		
Promoter/initiator	Talkual	Type of entity	Private/industry/business
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2020-	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	Website: https://www.talkualfoods.com Contact: info@talkualfoods.com , telephone: +34 722 19 74 52		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food Waste prevention		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: farmers		
Objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To reduce and combat food waste, giving a second chance to fruit and vegetables that are not sold in large supermarkets. To re-educate customers To offer job opportunities to people at risk of social exclusion, collaborating with ASPID (organization at regional level working for inclusion of people with disabilities) To be a loudspeaker for agriculture and the work carried out by the primary sector in the countryside, which is why they are committed to local and seasonal products. To help reduce plastic waste coming from packaging. 		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TALKUAL operates as an online platform offering healthy food choices while addressing food waste. They collaborate with small-scale farmers to rescue imperfect yet nutritious fruits and vegetables rejected by large retailers due to aesthetic standards. TALKUAL buys fruit and vegetables from all over Spain (being deals with small farmers preferred), performs quality control in their warehouse in Bellpuig, packs the product and ships it all over the country to their customers. 90% are private individuals and the other 10% are companies, such as Alsa or Decathlon, which send them to their employees.
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recover those imperfect fruits and vegetables rejected by large supermarkets Reuse those products in good condition initially discarded.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> News piece at El Pais. Link News piece at El Economista. Link
Related costs	No costs specified, may be related to staff and workers contraction, Transportation and communication channels
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Mobile app and online platform: Google Play , Apple store
Impact and sustainability	<p>Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social: Creation of Jobs (directly and indirectly) as the project has created full time-jobs for the team; job opportunities to people at risk of social exclusion, collaborating with ASPID. Alliances with 95 small farmers all over the Iberian peninsula, helping them sell their "imperfect" products. 38.773 People who have received TALKUAL at home. Environmental: Reduction of food waste (2.397.239 Kg of rescued fruit and vegetables); 3.595.859 N° of plastic bags saved, 4.938 Tons of CO₂ avoided; 373.969 Liters of water saved;
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business model (privately financed)
Social innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business Models: TALKUAL's social innovation lies in its holistic approach to addressing multiple interconnected issues within the food system Knowledge Transfer: TALKUAL engages in knowledge transfer by raising awareness about food waste and sustainable consumption practices
Challenges and barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market Acceptance/Public perception: Convincing consumers to purchase imperfect products. Financial Sustainability: Ensuring the financial sustainability of the business model while paying fair prices to farmers and keeping produce affordable for consumers. Competition: Facing competition from traditional supermarkets and other food retailers Identifying and Accessing Farmers: Locating and reaching out to farmers who may be interested in participating

4.6 Io non spreco

Figure 15. Campaign logo. Source: [Youtube channel](#)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Io Non Spreco		
Country/region	Italy / Lombardia		
Promoter/initiator	Milano Ristorazione Spa	Type of entity	Collective catering operator
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2022 -	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	Website promoter: Milano Ristorazione Email Secretary Milano Ristorazione		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food (Food surplus)		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Objectives:	Reduction of Food Waste and Redistribution: Recover surplus bread and unconsumed fruits from school cafeterias for redistribution to non-profit organizations and charitable structures in the area.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement of schools in the recovery of unconsumed bread and fruits. • Collaboration with the Association “<i>Banco Alimentare della Lombardia – Siticibo</i>”. • Distributed collection network across various schools. 		

Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	Reduction: Reducing food waste through recovery and redistribution. Recovery: Recovering unconsumed bread and fruits. Reuse: Reusing food for charitable purposes.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability Balance. Link to pdf https://www.bancoalimentare.it/ • A recipe book with 23 recipes against Food waste was distributed (in Italian, under requirement in webpage).
Related costs	The only costs are related to logistics because volunteers are involved in food collection and distribution.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<i>Not required</i>
Impact and sustainability	In the 2022/23 school year, more than 50 schools were involved, collecting more than 17.100 kg of bread and almost 39.000 kg of uneaten fruit. For the 2023/24 school year, the joint aim is to intensify this network, in order to make the collection even more widespread, while also accepting requests from voluntary associations operating close to schools.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italy Good Samaritan Law Legge del Buon Samaritano (Law n 155, 2003) -16/07/2023) https://www.bancoalimentare.it/news/legge-del-buon-samaritano-dieci-anni-recuperate-oltre-2-milioni-di-porzioni-di-piatti-pronti • Legge Gadda (Law n°166, 14/09/2016) https://www.bancoalimentare.it/legge-gadda
Social innovation	Established initiative involving schools, third-sector entities, and volunteer associations. Promotes solidarity culture among citizens. Includes a change on how private business operate (restoration services in schools) recognising social value. Develops partnerships between private and third sector (food banks)
Challenges and barriers	Legislative framework: Normative barriers removed in Italy by Good Samaritan Law, and Legge Gadda, may exist in other countries (i.e. Ireland has not a Good Samaritan Law), Network Expansion: Challenges in intensifying the network, logistical coordination, potential challenges related to awareness and participation from schools.

4.7 Il Riso che sostiene

Figure 16. Rice farm associated to project. Source: [Greenstyle.it](https://www.risogallo.it)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Il Riso che Sostiene		
Country/region	Italy / Lombardia		
Promoter/initiator	Riso Gallo SpA	Type of entity	Food Industry
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2019-	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.risogallo.it/ilrisochesostiene/economia-circolare/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food Waste		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> civil society/NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: certified organic farms		
Objectives:	Circular Economy and Valorisation of Rice By-Products: Generate value from rice processing by-products, transforming them into materials for bio-construction, furnishings, and clothing dyes following circular principles.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	Community Involvement: Currently, a community of 155 certified agricultural enterprises in Piemonte and Lombardia regions has joined the initiative, adhering to the FSA (Farm Sustainability Assessment)		

	<p>protocol, one of the internationally recognized standards for agricultural sustainability. The “<i>Rice Agreement</i>”, endorsed by the participating agricultural companies, advocates for eight simple rules, including the prohibition of using glyphosate directly on crops and the restriction on the use of purification sludges.</p> <p>Visionary Entrepreneurial Collaborations: <i>Il riso che Sostiene</i> is possible thanks to the participation in visionary entrepreneurial ventures like Rice House, Mogu, and Gruppo Albini.</p>
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<p>Recovery and recycle: Use of by-products for bio-construction, furnishings, and dyes. Creation of new materials for various applications. The company collaborates and provides support to <u>Rice House</u>, an innovative Italian entrepreneurial entity in which Riso Gallo holds a portion of the shareholding. The rice husk (lolla) and bran (pula, equivalent to wheat bran) are used to produce plaster. For thermal and acoustic insulation, both the rice husk and rice straw fibres are utilized. In addition, the company has initiated a collaboration with <u>Mogu</u>, an SME developing fully circular products for interior furnishings based on fungal biofabrication processes (mycelium technology) and the reuse of low-value raw materials. Riso Gallo has also recently embarked on a project with <u>Gruppo Albini</u>, a significant company specializing in the production of high-quality fabrics, to reuse the cooking water from Black Rice for the natural dyeing of fabrics destined for high fashion using production waste generated during the hydrothermal treatment phase.</p>
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project manifesto. Link
Related costs	The initiative costs (logistic, technology, manufacturing) are covered by products sales
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Fungal Bio-Fabrication (Mycelium Technology) with the use of innovative processes like fungal bio-fabrication for creating furnishings. Mogu's cutting-edge technology is based on mycelium, the vegetative stage of mushrooms.
Impact and sustainability	Agreements have been established with other partners (Bio-construction, furnishings and Fabrics and natural dyeing) to expand the initiative to other value chains
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Sale of sustainable products to fund the activities (circular business model)
Social innovation	Sustainability and Creativity: valorisation of by-products through innovative collaborations. Development of social housing.
Challenges and barriers	<p>Project Scalability: adapting and scaling circular projects to maximize impact. Need to engage further agricultural actors to extend the initiative.</p> <p>Technology: need to install separation technologies for the waste flows; technologies for valorisation (with fungi or to produce dye) needed in the region.</p> <p>Logistics: to transport the materials from the farm/agriculture company to the waste manager, and to the valorisation companies, need for arrangements to use the waste collected.</p>

4.8 Da Chicco a Chicco

Figure 17. Recycling of exhausted coffee and aluminium caps. Source: [Nespresso](#)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Da Chicco a Chicco		
Country/region	Italy		
Promoter/initiator	Nestlé Nespresso S.A	Type of entity	Food Industry
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2011 - Active	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.nespresso.com/it/it/caffe-sostenibile		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food waste (coffee) and food packaging (aluminium)		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Objectives:	This initiative supports both circular economy and social engagement. Circular Economy: The goal is to implement circularity, technological innovation, and social commitment by giving a second life to used capsules and transforming coffee wastes into fertilizer for rice cultivation. Aluminium Recycle: capsules are transformed into new objects such as pens, bicycles, etc. Coffee Waste Recycle: The used coffee is sent to a composting plant for transformation into compost, which is then subsequently donated to a rice field in the province of Novara.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	Nespresso has implemented its own collection system (<i>Nespresso Boutiques</i> , ecological islands, and specialized services in the		

	<p>respective provinces). Additionally, throughout the province of Lecco and in municipalities managed by the municipal company <u>CEM Ambiente</u> in the provinces of Monza Brianza, Milan, and Lodi, a collection service is active that allows consumers to dispose of the capsules in the lightweight multi-material bag without the need to return them to designated collection points. The initiative now also involves another major coffee seller, Illy Caffè.</p>
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse: Aluminium from capsules is recycled to create new objects and coffee is used as fertilizer • Recovery: Recovery of aluminium and coffee through dedicated processes. • Recycling: Aluminium is recycled, and spent coffee is transformed into natural compost for rice cultivation.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website. Link. • Video on YouTube. Link • Terms and conditions of the campaign. Link to pdf.
Related costs	<p>Costs for “<i>Da Chicco a Chicco</i>” are basically related to 3 different Typologies: (i) Logistics for the collection of the used capsule: (ii) Technology for the recycling/transformation and (iii) manufacturing. Over 7 million euros are devoted to developing and implementing the collection system.</p>
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<p>The collaboration between Nespresso, Cial, and Silea utilizes waste recognition and separation technologies from the Seruso plant in Verderio. There, aluminium recovery is carried out using a screening system capable of dividing the waste stream into three fractions – fine, intermediate, and coarse – through the Eddy current separator technology (ECS) that uses magnetism to collect aluminium, separating it from non-conductive materials such as glass, plastic, paper, or wood.</p>
Impact and sustainability	<p>Environmental impact: Recovery of almost 10.000 tons of capsules, generating over 570 tons of aluminium, over 5.000 tons of spent coffee. Social impact: Donation of rice to Banco Alimentare in Lombardia, Lazio, Piemonte, and Puglia, equivalent to about 5 million plates for those in need. 1 million rice dishes equivalent donated in 2023 alone thanks to the “<i>Da Chicco a Chicco</i>” project, totalling 90 tons of rice (14% increase compared to 2022).</p>
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<p>Direct Investment: Nespresso has directly invested over 7 million euros to develop and implement the collection system.</p>
Social innovation	<p>Community Engagement: The program involves consumers encouraging them to return used capsules and contribute to rice production for donation. Social Innovation: The rice produced through this natural fertilizer is later repurchased by Nespresso and finally donated to the “<i>Banco Alimentare della Lombardia</i>” and “<i>Banco Alimentare del Lazio</i>”, becoming a support for needy people.</p>
Challenges and barriers	<p>Logistical Challenges: Coordination in the collection, processing, and distribution of recycled materials. Scaling the Project: Involving other coffee producers and logistics. Awareness: Challenges in raising consumer awareness and promoting capsule recycling, Nespresso prepared a rewards program that varies over time.</p>

4.9 Too good to go

Figure 18. Recovery of food through the Too good to go app. Source: [Scattidigusto](#)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Too Good To Go		
Country/region	Global		
Promoter/initiator	Too Good To Go	Type of entity	IT operator
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2015 - Active	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.toogoodtogo.com/it		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved (related to A2C)	Food (Food surplus)		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> civil society/NGOs, <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities <input type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Municipal/regional)		
Objectives:	Reduce food waste by connecting merchants with unsold products and consumers eager to buy discounted food.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	Too Good To Go provides a digital platform (available for IOS and Android) allowing merchants to upload their unsold products at discounted prices. Consumers use the app to browse nearby offers,		

	purchase packages of unsold food, and pick them up at the designated store or restaurant.
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery: Recovering economic value from unsold products. • Recycling: Promoting recycling of packaging through sustainable practices.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact report 2023. Link • Observatory of food waste report. Link
Related costs	The initiative costs include: (i) app and website management; (ii) logistic costs; (iii) packaging. These are covered by product sales, since the stores that sell their products in the app pay a percentage of their sales to the application.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Mobile App: The digital platform serves as a key tool, efficiently connecting merchants and consumers.
Impact and sustainability	<p>In 2022, 80.000 merchants collaborated with Too Good to Go and 79 million of non-wasted meals were distributed. The following impacts were achieved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of Food Waste: Contributes to a significant reduction in food waste by saving good but unsold food. • Awareness: Raises awareness about food waste and promotes more sustainable behaviours among consumers and merchants. • Economic Benefits: Provides merchants with a way to recover some value from unsold products and consumers the opportunity to save on quality food. • Reduced Environmental Impact: Decreases the environmental impact associated with food and packaging disposal, contributing to overall sustainability.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Transaction-based Model: Too Good To Go operates on a transactional basis, where businesses pay a fee or percentage for each item sold through the platform.
Social innovation	Community Engagement: Involves both businesses and consumers in a social initiative aimed at addressing the broader issue of food waste.
Challenges and barriers	<p>Business Participation: Convincing businesses to join the platform and sell surplus items at a discount can be challenging.</p> <p>Consumer Adoption: Encouraging consumers to embrace the concept of purchasing surplus food can face resistance.</p> <p>Logistical Challenges: Coordinating the timely pickup of surplus items and ensuring they meet quality standards presents logistical challenges.</p> <p>Regulatory Compliance: Navigating and adhering to food safety and regulatory requirements in different regions can be complex.</p> <p>Scaling Issues: Expanding the platform to new regions and scaling the impact globally may encounter cultural and logistical barriers.</p>

4.10 Maisto bankas

Figure 19. Maisto bankas logo in Lithuania. Source: [sustainablegastro](https://sustainablegastro.com)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	"Maisto Bankas" (eng. Food bank)		
Country/region	Lithuania		
Promoter/initiator	Independent charity and support fund	Type of entity	Other
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2001-	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.maistobankas.lt/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food production, food market		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> civil society/NGOs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations	
Objectives:	Tackle food waste and provide food assistance to those in need. "Maisto Bankas" promotes responsible food consumption, rational nutrition, efficient resource use, and public solidarity in the fight against food waste, protection of the environment, and help of the needy.		
Intervention type/structure and methodology	Food aid is collected and distributed in 84 cities and districts across Lithuania, with distribution taking place in 203 areas. Volunteers help organize the received food products and hand them over to social organizations that care for the needy - load, sort, pack, position in the warehouse. Different actions are performed to gather donations.		

Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	The 9R's are: Reuse, Recycle, Recover
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website of Eurofoodbank: https://www.eurofoodbank.org/ • Costs and impacts (in Lithuanian). Link
Related costs	Personnel costs (109 official individuals are employed).
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Website portal, media channels.
Impact and sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the creation of jobs • a decrease of waste generation • a decrease of population hunger • an increase of social community
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the European Aid to the Most Deprived Fund (EPLSAF) • Charity and initiatives for donations
Social innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community engagement: Campaigns in large shopping chains (MAXIMA, IKI, RIMI, LIDL, Utena prekyba) where citizens are invited to buy longer-lasting food products for those in need (276 non-governmental organizations participate). Actions in mass media to gather donations during concerts ("A call that nourishes"). Food support to "Maisto bankas" containers in "RIMI" stores and RIMI food containers in restaurants, cafes and other catering establishments, collecting food products/dishes that cannot be sold to be transferred to feed the needy. • Education and training: The "Maisto bankas" Academy is a training program for beneficiaries of the European Aid to the Most Deprived Fund (EPLSAF), during which professional lecturers conduct lessons on job search opportunities and how to eat tastier and more wholesome food and save money. Training is held in various regions
Challenges and barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shortage of Regulation awareness although it was cleared by the organisation that donation does not incur any cost. • Financial resources: the project has applied for further funding with other NGOs. • Logistics and transportation: Availability of recycling stations. Thanks to the app, people can be recruited to transport the waste to stations and get money for it (circular economy business model) • Finding suppliers for goods and services needed. One-by-one engagement activities. • Regulations limit transferability/scale-up: local authorities are adjusting rules and regulations at the community/city/state level.

4.11 Biomotorai

Figure 20. Collecting cooking oil at restaurant to be recycled by Biomotorai.

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	JSC Biomotorai		
Country/region	Lithuania		
Promoter/initiator	Private investment	Type of entity	Private investment
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2006 -	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://www.biomotorai.lt/en/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Cooking oil recycling		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations	
Objectives:	<p>“Biomotorai” – the leader of used cooking oil collection and processing in the Baltic region. Such unusable oil is cleaned and used for biofuel production by other biodiesel production companies in Europe. The company has direct connection with legal entities as clients, also handles oil that is collected from residents and promotes social activities to increase awareness that used oils and greases are harmful waste.</p>		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	<p>The company applies the latest and most modern technologies, which allow our clients to order conveniently transportation of waste by mobile app, to quickly formalize transfer by e-consignment, to receive a detailed report on the quantities and quality transferred</p> <p>Residents of the Vilnius region are invited to collect used oil residues in a sustainable and convenient way in the designated 3.5-liter containers. From October 2024, special 3.5-liter containers for the collection of used oil were distributed to residents of the Vilnius region at large waste collection sites administered by the municipality. 44,900 units were distributed to residents of the Vilnius region. Unusable oil stored in these or any other containers can be delivered to all large waste collection sites operating in the Vilnius region</p>
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<p>Rethink - reevaluating consumption habits and waste management practices; Reduce - reducing the amount of fossil resources, the amount of waste entering the wastewater and the amount of waste polluting the soil surfaces; Recycle – systematic collecting and processing of the used cooking oil into biofuel.</p>
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brochure (lithuanian): https://www.delfi.lt/projektai/eko-energetika/ar-kada-susimastete-kuo-pavirsta-kebabu-kioske-likes-aliejus-76935659 • Social media: Facebook
Related costs	Conventional business model – joint stock company (JSC)
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	The know-how, belonging to the company, for treatment and cleaning of the used oil.
Impact and sustainability	Overall, community-based schemes for used cooking oil collection and processing have the potential to deliver both immediate and long-term sustainable impacts by addressing environmental, health, economic, and social issues within communities. Through active engagement, education, and collaboration, these initiatives can contribute to building resilient and environmentally responsible societies.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Company's private funds, and municipality funds for containers to supply the residents.
Social innovation	In three months, 2,325 kilograms of used oil were collected in the "We are building Lithuania!" project of social initiatives, in which 14 schools and kindergartens of Joniškis district participated. As many as 166 special containers were built to collect oil in educational institutions. All used oil will be processed and become part of the ecological fuel—biodiesel. It is estimated that the collected oil will allow the production of approximately 1,813 litres of biodiesel, with which a passenger car could travel over 22,000 kilometres.
Challenges and barriers	By proactively addressing the challenges such as convenient recycling station availability for residents, lack of awareness and participation, regulations for treated oil application and implementing appropriate contingency measures, community-based schemes for used cooking oil collection and processing can enhance their effectiveness, sustainability, and long-term viability. Collaboration, innovation, and community engagement are key to overcoming barriers and achieving success in such initiatives.

4.12 Gražinti Verta

Figure 21. Promotional video of Gražinti verta. Source: [Youtube](#)

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	“Gražinti Verta”		
Country/region	Whole country, Lithuania		
Promoter/initiator	Non Profit Public institution "Užstato Sistemų Administratorius" (USAD) and founders	Type of entity	NGO or CSO
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2006 -	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://grazintiverta.lt/en/about/74		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Plastic packaging (PET bottles), glass, metal		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Objectives:	The objectives of the system can be inferred as follows: a) Environmental protection: Waste Reduction and resource efficiency; b) Stakeholder Engagement; c) Compliance and Accountability; d) Economic Viability. By addressing these objectives, the system aims to create a more sustainable and circular economy within the beverage industry, benefiting both society and the environment.		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manufacturers and importers supply beverages for the consumers who pay both the price for the product and the deposit for the packaging. 2. Consumer returns the packaging (labelled) to the retailer using reverse vending machines and the retailer reimburses the deposit to the consumer. 3. Retailer returns reusable packaging to manufacturers, USAD calculates it, and reimburses the deposit for retailer accordingly. 4. The manufacturer pays USAD the price for the packaging. <p>The deposit for 1 unit of package (bottle) is 10 euro cents, applicable to the following types of one-way packaging: glass (except for some fruit wine, fruit-wine-based drinks and fruit-wine cocktails in one-way glass packaging); PET; metal.</p>
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<p>Reuse. The system encourages the return of packaging for potential reuse.</p> <p>Recycle. The primary goal of the deposit return system is to promote recycling by incentivizing consumers to return beverage packaging for recycling or reuse.</p>
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<p>It is possible to follow online the number of returned packaging live: https://grazintiverta.lt/en/about/69</p>
Related costs	<p>Industry fees for manufacturers and importers are set so that the net financial result of USAD would equal to zero. More info in this link</p> <p>Operational and financial results plan for 2022: Link to report</p>
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Reverse vending machines
Impact and sustainability	<p>In Lithuania USAD collects 9 out of 10 beverage cans, one-way glass and plastic bottles, marked with the deposit system mark, placed on the market each year. The system contributes to a circular approach by reducing the consumption of raw materials, minimizing waste generation, and promoting the reuse and recycling of resources within the beverage supply chain. According to public opinion, the system contributes to the clean-up of the environment, helps to reduce the amount of litter found in forests, lakes and other natural sites.</p>
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<p>Founding members are Lithuanian Association of Breweries, Association of Lithuanian Trade Enterprises, Lithuanian Natural Mineral Water Manufacturers Association. Sometimes the deposit system is adapted in institutions to collect support funds. USAD receives revenue from 3 sources: subsidies for beverage producers and importers (main source of funding, 50%); secondary raw materials sold (30%), not withdrawn deposit (deposit for unreturned packaging, 20%).</p>
Social innovation	<p>Several factors can be considered as social innovation, as they address social and environmental challenges: a) Deposit Return System. Implementing a deposit return system incentivizes consumers to return packaging for recycling, reducing litter and promoting environmental stewardship, while fostering a sense of responsibility among consumers towards waste management. b) Collaboration. The involvement of multiple stakeholders, including manufacturers, importers, retailers, citizens, and a deposit management entity (USAD), highlights a collaborative approach to addressing environmental challenges. c) Behavioural Change. The deposit return system prompts a shift in consumer behaviour towards recycling and waste reduction.</p>
Challenges and barriers	<p>The system requires collaboration among stakeholders, innovative solutions, and ongoing commitment to promoting sustainable practices.</p>

	<p>come at their convenient time. The activities of Sapięga's gardeners exemplify circularity by emphasizing resource efficiency, community sharing and collaboration, and external knowledge exchange, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient local food system. More info. Activity We Protect The Environment. The Community annually organises Coastal (Riva Neris) management and cleaning initiatives. The initiative reflects circularity by promoting community engagement, knowledge sharing, recognition of environmental achievements, and proactive efforts to address environmental challenges. More info.</p>
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	<p>Rethink - fosters resource efficiency, community collaboration, and environmental stewardship; Reduce - reducing consumption and waste generation through mindful resource management, product design innovation, and behavioural shifts of the community members. Reuse - encourages community members to repurpose, refurbish, and exchange goods, materials, and resources; Recycle - practices to systematically collect, sort, and process materials for reintegration into the production cycle.</p>
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<p>Video about activities of Community: http://www.antakalnieciai.lt/video-irasai/ All activities of Community: http://www.antakalnieciai.lt/apie/</p>
Related costs	<p>The community uses a hall in a municipality building on the territory of Sapięgu Park. It has an annual membership fee. As an NGO, it prepares and submits Project proposals for Community activities.</p>
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	<p>No technologies required</p>
Impact and sustainability	<p>Community empowerment: Organizing environmental hikes, events, and educational programs raises awareness about environmental issues and fosters a culture of sustainability within the community. Reduction of resources consumption: By cultivating vegetables locally, the initiative reduces the carbon footprint associated with food transportation and promotes biodiversity within the park environment. Capacity building and training: providing members with agricultural skills and resources to grow their own food, promoting self-sufficiency and food security. Long-term sustainability: Collaboration with municipal authorities and participation in European initiatives (project RU: RBAN) provide institutional support and resources for ongoing environmental conservation efforts.</p>
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	<p>Membership, funds for NGO, project activities.</p>
Social innovation	<p>Community-driven approach to address social and environmental challenges, fostering inclusivity, collaboration, knowledge exchange, and collective action for positive change. Active involvement of residents in environmental conservation efforts demonstrates a bottom-up approach to addressing environmental challenges.</p>
Challenges and barriers	<p>Lack of sufficient resources, such as funding, tools, and materials, may hinder the expansion and sustainability of the gardening initiative. Seasonality of gardening activities depending on weather conditions and growing seasons. Reluctance or disability of individuals to commit time and effort to gardening due to other obligations or interests. Rapid urbanization and development may threaten the natural environment and green spaces in Antakalnis</p>

4.14 Barrio La Pinada

Figure 23. Building constructed with recycled materials in La Pinada

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Barrio La Pinada: Spain's First Co-Created Sustainable Neighborhood		
Country/region	Valencia, Spain		
Promoter/initiator	Zubi Cities (Zubi Labs)	Type of entity	Private Sector, Public-private collaboration
Start date (year)-End date (year)	2017	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	Website: https://zubicities.com/proyectos/barrio-la-pinada/ Contact: hola@barriolapinada.es		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	The initiative at Barrio La Pinada potentially involves multiple value chains in the circular economy (sustainable urban development, green building, renewable energy, and waste management)		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Media <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Universities		
Objectives:	Co-create a sustainable neighbourhood with emphasis on green living, efficient resource management, and community well-being		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	Educational spaces and co-creation workshops with future residents and expert professionals to collaboratively develop innovative and efficient solutions integrating sustainability in its three dimensions (social, economic, and environmental). Organization of the “Rethinking Cities” congress to discuss topics like energy, water, and data. The project is under development due to legal requirements
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R’s or any other.	Rethink is applied in envisioning the urban design to prioritize a sustainable lifestyle. Reduce is evident in the efficient use of resources and minimization of CO ₂ emissions. Use of recycled building materials, building with energy efficiency criteria. Reduction of plastics, promotion of local products through food markets. Reuse is promoted through shared community services and amenities. On-demand shared electric mobility with the city centre. Repair is incorporated into the design for disassembly, using reversible connections.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular economy guidelines: Link to pdf • Presentation. Link to pdf • Press dossier. Link to pdf
Related costs	Not provided. May be related to investment in renewable materials and technologies, infrastructure for sustainable energy and water management, and the systems required for efficient waste reduction and resource recovery.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Barrio La Pinada incorporates enabling technologies that support its circularity principles: sustainable construction methods, renewable energy systems like solar panels and geothermal energy, smart water management systems, and innovative waste treatment solutions such as anaerobic digesters for biogas production. Urban design also features permeable pavements and sustainable drainage systems
Impact and sustainability	There are no reports available on actual impacts. Environmental impact: fostering sustainable living and reducing environmental footprints. This includes renewable energy usage, waste reduction, and water management, ensuring that the community remains resilient and self-sufficient. Social impact: promoting resilience and self-sufficiency, and cultivating an environmentally conscious culture among residents. Sustainability: educational projects to carry circular principles forward by future generations.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	EU funding: It's part of the "Smart Sustainable Districts" program within Climate KIC by the EU's European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). Collaboration with public administrations: 30% are expected to be social housing.
Social innovation	Barrio La Pinada's approach to social innovation is multifaceted, emphasizing community engagement and co-creation from the outset. It includes aspects such as: Activism (Promoting environmental and social initiatives); Community Involvement (urban innovation workshops focusing on key themes like energy, water, and social innovation); Education (Montessori school to foster a culture of lifelong learning and sustainability); Inclusivity (Ensuring the neighbourhood is accessible, equitable, and caters to a diverse community)
Challenges and barriers	Challenges in attracting residents who are aligned with the community's participatory and unconventional living model.

4.15 Circularcity

Figure 24. Logo of the Circularcity initiative

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Circularicity: Civic Crowdfunding for the Circular Economy.		
Country/region	Capannori, Lucca, Italy		
Promoter/initiator	Municipality of Capannori with the collaboration of Sociolab, Eppela	Type of entity	Combination of Local Government and Non-Governmental Organization
Start date (year)- End date (year)	June- November 2017	Status	Completed
Link or contact for further information*	https://open.toscana.it/web/circularicity/ Contact: community of Cappanori. Link		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Focus on circular economy practices including recycling, creative reuse, and sustainable living		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Universities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> civil society/NGOs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations		
Objectives:	To stimulate innovative civil society projects focused on sustainability, recycling, and creative reuse; to encourage citizen participation in public		

	spending through crowdfunding; to experiment with collaborative solutions between citizens, institutions, and communities.
Intervention type/structure and methodology	A participatory process involving crowdfunding, workshops, social media, and collaboration between public bodies and citizens, aiming to develop civic capacities and influence decisions of government and public bodies Supported by Tuscany's Regional Authority for the Promotion of Participation
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	Circularicity employed a holistic approach to circular economy principles, fostering projects that embody the 9R's: Rethink - rethink consumption habits; Reduce - reduce waste. Project ConServe with Caritas promoting a laboratory to fight food waste/loss; Reuse - reuse materials; Repair, Refurbish - repair items instead of discarding them, refurbish old goods; Recycle, Recover —recycle efficiently, and recover resources. Use of 3D printing with to create goods with recycled plastic, urban mining for building materials.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participedia infosheet: Link • Programme. Link to pdf • Funded projects. Link • Capannori ZeroWaste: Link to pdf
Related costs	For the Circularicity project, the crowdfunding efforts through the Eppela platform allowed each of the five projects to achieve 50% of their funding goals through community support. The Municipality of Capannori complemented this by providing the remaining 50%, contributing a total of €20,000 to support these sustainable local economy initiatives.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Circularicity supported projects that leverage technology for sustainability: a 3D printing initiative recycling plastic into useful items, a scheme to reclaim electrical components, a lab targeting food waste reduction, a program for land and job restoration, and a platform for exchanging goods using a novel currency.
Impact and sustainability	40% of waste reduction (average waste went from 1,92 kg to 1,18 kg/person/year); Separate collection increased rate to 82%; Residual waste per capita reduced by 57%. Waste tariffs for residents have been reduced by 20% while 93 tonnes of items were dropped at the Reuse Centre. Capannori became an international example. Inspired by its success, today nearly 400 European municipalities are walking the path towards Zero Waste
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Funded through civic crowdfunding and partially by the regional government.
Social innovation	Use of Social Innovation Camp method in the two-day immersive workshop organized according to the method: competition between innovative ideas, which uses the web Use of Business Model Canvas, a time schedule and a commercial plan (Business Plan) are constructed, and crowdfunding strategies are defined.
Challenges and barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of transparency in co-financing information and the absence of detailed documentation during evaluation phases. • The two-step project selection process limited the number of initiatives that could be supported, necessitating substantial resources for training and crowdsourcing support. • No post-project monitoring to assess long-term impacts.

4.16 CONSERVE

Figure 25. Different types of conserves made in the CONSERVE project

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	CONSERVE		
Country/region	Tuscany, Italy		
Promoter/initiator	Caritas Diocesana, Calafata Farm, Rinascita Cooperative, Slow Food Association, CIA - Confederazione degli Agricoltori, Equinozio	Type of entity	Collaboration between NGOs, local farms, and association
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2016	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	L'Unitaria Cooperativa https://www.lunitaria.it/consERVE/ info@lunitaria.it		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Food waste reduction		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Local farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> civil society/NGOs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations		

Objectives	To reduce food waste by transforming surplus agricultural produce into quality canned goods, while promoting employment for disadvantaged individuals.
Intervention type/structure and methodology	Establishing a food processing laboratory to process surplus produce into canned goods, involving the community and various partners.
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	The project embodies Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle by efficiently using surplus produce and creating new products, thus reducing waste and promoting sustainability.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Piece of news: Link
Related costs	Laboratory machinery (€100,000), employment costs for commercial and administrative activities (€50,000), and additional support for disadvantaged workers (€12,000).
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Food processing and preservation technology.
Impact and sustainability	There are no reports available on actual impacts. On sustainability: Filled a gap in the local food transformation chain, created jobs for disadvantaged individuals, and produced 20 different types of seasonal products.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Civic crowdfunding, contributions from local associations, and regional funding
Social innovation	Conserve represents a potent example of social innovation by engaging the local community in sustainable practices. It provides employment to disadvantaged individuals, integrating them into the workforce and promoting inclusivity. The initiative supports local agriculture and reduces food waste, transforming surplus produce into high-quality canned goods. Through civic crowdfunding and collaborations with local partners, Conserve enhances community cohesion, preserves local food traditions, and promotes a circular economy. This model demonstrates the potential for local initiatives to drive significant social and environmental impact.
Challenges and barriers	Securing necessary economic and material resources, ensuring competitive market costs, and managing human relations.

4.17 Restart Project

Figure 26. Screenshot of video at Restart Youtube channel

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Restart Project		
Country/region	London, UK		
Promoter/initiator	The Restart Project, a people-powered social enterprise	Type of entity	NGO
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2013	Status	Ongoing
Link or contact for further information*	https://therestartproject.org/about/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Electronic Waste		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Objectives	To reduce electronic waste and extend the lifespan of electronics through repair, to promote a culture of repair and reuse, and to advocate for policies that support the right to repair.		

Intervention type/structure and methodology	Organizing community repair events, training individuals in repair skills, advocating for sustainable policies, and compiling a global directory of repair businesses.
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	The Restart Project embodies the Repair, Reuse, and Recycle aspects of the 9R's by empowering people to fix their own electronics, thus preventing waste and encouraging a shift away from a throwaway culture to a more sustainable model of consumption.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video at youtube (see Figure 26) Link • 2023 Narrative and financial report. Link
Related costs	Funded by over £190,000 from The National Lottery Climate Action Fund for the Fixing Factory project, additional support from EU-funded projects, and contributions from local organizations and foundations.
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Use of digital platforms for education, community engagement, and advocacy; tools and resources for electronic repairs.
Impact and sustainability	There are no reports available on actual impacts. On sustainability: Successfully diverted thousands of electronic items from waste through repair events, influenced policy discussions on the right to repair, and raised public awareness on the importance of reducing e-waste.
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Supported by grants, donations, and community crowdfunding.
Social innovation	The Restart Project innovates socially by creating a repair-focused community movement, contributing to environmental sustainability, and influencing policy for a circular economy.
Challenges and barriers	Challenges include changing the consumer culture from disposal to repair, navigating legal and policy barriers to repair, and securing resources to scale the initiative.

5 Summary of results

The results of the community-based scheme performed in Alhama de Murcia city market have been summarized in the same template used to analyse other schemes in this deliverable

Table 1. Summary of the results of Alhama Community Based scheme

GENERAL INFORMATION			
Title of the community-based scheme	Selective Collection at the Street Market		
Country/region	Alhama de Murcia, Spain		
Promoter/initiator	Fundación Primafrío	Type of entity	NGO,
Start date (year)- End date (year)	2022-2024	Status	Finished
Link or contact for further information*	https://fundacionprimafrío.com/agro2circular/		
DESCRIPTION			
Value chain(s) involved	Vegetable and Fruit Waste		
Stakeholders involved (please check all that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local businesses <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Media <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing industries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens (individuals) <input type="checkbox"/> Retail sector <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Civil society/NGOs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public utilities (Municipal/regional) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To engage the public and promote circular social practices among citizens, To raise awareness about the A2C project and food waste, To perform a pilot activity for selective collection of waste generated at the market Subsequent transfer to the Technology Center for recovery 		
Intervention type/structure methodology and	Year 1 - installation of containers for the selective collection of fruit and vegetables. - Transfer to the Technology Centre (CTNC). - Installation of a marquee and stall for the dissemination of the project and concepts of the circular economy.		

	<p>Year 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness-raising activities, awareness-raising and workshops, promoting waste reduction and sustainability. - Conducting surveys
Circular strategy(-ies). strategies based on the 9R's or any other.	The project takes up, disseminates and embodies the concept of the 7Rs, namely Reduce, Reuse, Remanufacture and Recycle through the efficient use of surpluses and the creation of new products, thus reducing waste and promoting sustainability through awareness-raising and sensitisation.
Resources available (videos, guidelines, reports, materials, links)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://ayuntamiento.alhamademurcia.es/noticia.asp?cat=9766 - https://sietediasalhama.com/noticia/15199/medio-ambiente/v/f-alhama-pionera-en-un-proyecto-de-economia-circular.html - https://revistaconecta.es/actualidad/alhama-de-murcia-el-ayuntamiento-de-alhama-se-suma-al-proyecto-europeo-agro2circular/?fbclid=IwAR3Z1jGaZqMFCBVkHPVvTEiWkIOvumrey3lEpBU2Znvw7wD0bl33VrnzC1E.
Related costs	Transportation: 2480.-€; merchandising and advertising elements: 1095_€; employment costs for training, commercial and administrative activities (10.765€)
Enabling technologies fostering circularity.	Research Technologies that have facilitated the elaboration of valorised products that have fostered circularity
Impact sustainability and	<p>Almost 4,500 people have been directly reached in environmental awareness talks, promoting knowledge and skills to raise awareness of the circular economy, conceived as an alternative, among others, to solve problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and other environmental problems.</p> <p>This programme proactively engages cities and citizens to become strongly involved, realising their enormous power to change lifestyles, promote change and advocate for long-term well-being.</p> <p>This community system manifests itself as an inclusive programme, reinforcing knowledge generation, acquisition and exchange, as well as promoting change, as an exemplary action based on a fluid dialogue between stakeholders.</p> <p>On sustainability: It brought the theoretical concepts of circular economy and research from the technical centres closer to the citizens, raising awareness, sensitisation and incorporation of sustainability criteria in their daily decisions and actions</p>
Financing Schemes or instruments used by the project.	Through the European funds of the Agro2circular Project (H2020 funding) and the Foundation's own resources.
Social innovation	<p>The Alhama Market community programme represents a powerful example of social innovation by engaging the local community in sustainable practices. The initiative has provided first-hand knowledge of the European A2C project research in the recovery of waste from the agri-food industry, which is so present and highly relevant in the area.</p> <p>It has provided practical knowledge of the circular economy, reinforcing its sustainable practices in this regard and allowing it to extend its scope of action to other decisions in its daily actions, such as responsible consumption, the</p>

	<p>fight against food waste and the promotion of recycling. It has provided the ground for business to flourish in this sector. It has boosted community cohesion by involving the community in decision making from the outset, and by making a strong commitment throughout the project. The initiative supports local agriculture and reduces food waste by transforming surplus food into high quality preserves. Through civic crowdfunding and collaboration with local partners, Conserve improves community cohesion, preserves local food traditions and promotes a circular economy. This model demonstrates the potential of local initiatives to drive significant social and environmental impact.</p>
<p>Challenges and barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Possibility of incorporating further seasonal products into the collection and research</i> • <i>Conducting workshops on giving products a second life, such as cooking workshops on food reuse</i> • <i>Establishing collection points in urban areas to bring recycling facilities closer to citizens; improving accessibility</i>

6 Evaluation of the results

Thanks to the street market community-based scheme, we were able to get feedback during the day-to-day contact with the citizens visiting the market and vendors, which has been useful for Agro2Circular to conclude that circular economy is already perceived as beneficial. The activity reached about 150 people per day, in a rough estimation, since a high variability was detected depending on weather conditions, coincidence with holidays or other local events.

The largest group of stakeholders reached were housewives along with pensioners, as the Alhama City market operates on the mornings of working day (Tuesday). Nevertheless, when the market took place during a scholar holiday, a higher affluence of students from primary and secondary schools was detected, many of them accompanied by relatives (mainly grandparents). It can be highlighted that those students that had participated in other project activities (such as talks, seminars or the videogames contests, framed within 8.3) attracted their relatives to the project booth at the street market, to explain what they have learnt about recycling and Circular Economy.

Another important group visiting the booth at the Alhama city market were the local political decision makers and public servants, for instance the technicians at the local development agencies that encouraged citizens and market vendors to participate in the activities, as well as counsellors of the City Hall, interested in the progress of the project.

The market vendors, and their associations, revealed as a key stakeholder participating in the project and encouraging citizens to reduce fruit and vegetable waste and to use biodegradable bags. Moreover, it was detected that many of them were interested in participating in the initiative, but their involvement was hindered since the products they sell (textiles, electronic devices, toys, other types of fruits and vegetables) were not included within the scope of the project.

1.Economic impact: the feedback obtained from citizens indicated that they consider Circular Economy as positive due to the generation of new job positions and the updating of existing ones. They declared that the activities carried out had helped them to save by avoiding the purchase of unnecessary products (fruit/vegetables/clothing), in line with the “refuse” and “rethink” strategies, the reduction of food waste and the promotion of new

business models based on reuse, such as second-hand clothing, according to “reuse” or “refurbish” strategy, which in addition contributes to diversifying the local economy.

2. Social impact: the community stated, through the feedback provided, that the activities in the booth had encouraged them to make responsible purchases, and they perceived an improvement in their quality of life through the acquisition of more durable products. They have been made aware of the second life that the products/objects they dispose of can have and of their multiple possibilities if they are deposited in the appropriate recycling container. All this entails a cultural and educational change that promotes a sustainable mentality, increasing environmental awareness.

3.Environmental impact: Both citizens and vendors who participated in the activity stated in their comments that they had learned through everyday examples provided at the stand and felt encouraged to apply the knowledge presented to them at home, reducing waste and minimizing waste generation by reusing products and materials. They felt that they had learned about how the exploitation of resources can be reduced and about alternatives, such as walking or cycling around the city. The workshops given on recycling and the different types of existing plastics were considered useful for reducing pollution in the municipality, and for promoting better water and soil conservation that would improve public health.

4. Innovation and Technology: this community-based scheme was revealed as a good opportunity to bring science and technology closer to society, as some of the products obtained during the project were showcased by the partners at the booth during some of the market days. Citizens and market vendors stated that they now can better recognise the importance of collaboration and the role of science and technological advances to improve our environment, stimulating innovation driven by research and development of new materials and recycling technologies. The knowledge-transfer, through the information and workshops provided at the booth (on different plastic types, waste management and recycling practices), was considered crucial for the success of the project, raising awareness of how the resources of a variety of stakeholders (industry, public administration, and research institutions) can be devoted to improving the planet.

In summary, what has had the greatest impact, according to visitors, is the commitment to innovation and collaboration, which encourages creativity in the design of durable and recyclable products and promotes a cultural shift towards more conscious consumption.

The community-based scheme can be considered a brilliant and necessary strategy that can be transferred to other municipalities, with the support of local administrations and civil society organisations, addressing some of the greatest challenges of our time: the scarcity of resources, environmental pollution and climate change. According to the feedback obtained, the community-based scheme could also be extended to other products present in the market.

The activity was considered to foster new forms of business, such as the collaborative economy and repair, that strengthen local communities. Being able to transform the way we produce and consume not only promotes environmental sustainability but also generates economic and social opportunities.

Through the activity, the project has also been able to gather feedback that has been transferred to local administrations to improve waste management and has received interest from policy makers; for instance, the City Counsellor on Environment stated the intention to accelerate the installation of containers for organic waste (the “brown container”), that needs to be approved by the regional government holding the competences on waste management. As a result, it has been suggested to install a suggestions box at the City Hall to continue collecting requests from the community, on circular economy issues.

While it is not a magic bullet and requires a massive mindset shift and political support, it can be considered a key pathway to a more sustainable and equitable future.

As for the other community-based schemes (CBS) analysed in this report, the following lessons can be extracted:

- Half of the CBS are started by civil society organisations, while the others are promoted by private companies.
- Those schemes initiated by civil society were found to require less technological inputs and be based on networking, while facing challenges related to funding or intensifying the network as they rely on the work on volunteers. On the other hand, the schemes initiated by private initiatives were related to recovery processes requiring more advanced technologies (recovering butts, oil, aluminium) and relied

on circular business models for funding (for instance, benefits from other branches) but were less rooted in communities.

- Some of the CBS found provided no details on the amount and the type of costs incurred, which hinders the evaluation of their impact, long term sustainability and transferability to other contexts
- Only 4 of the CBS relied on the participation of the different stakeholders (public administrations, industry, CSOs). This collaboration is considered necessary for the long-term sustainability of the initiative, providing with knowledge, skills and resources (i.e. funding) to engage communities in the implementation.
- Adequate policies and legislative measures are needed for the implementation of community-based schemes, for instance, facilitating recovery of packaging through deposit return systems or reducing barriers to the handover of surplus food to charities or non-profits.

7 Conclusions

Community-led based initiatives such as the activity carried out in the local market in Alhama through Agro2circular play a key role for involving local communities and citizenship in circular economy initiatives: they allow to raise awareness on the importance of the topic and promote a change of mindset towards sustainable consumption habits; to collect valuable feedback on their needs and expectations ensuring the responsiveness of R+D activities; and to bring stakeholders (specially those usually difficult to reach due to sociocultural barriers) closer to European projects results, allowing them to better recognise the importance of collaboration in innovation and the role of science and technological advances to improve our environment.

To enhance the impact of community-based schemes, the organisation should **consider potential synergies with other public participation activities** to be exploited during the organisation of the activity. Some examples that yielded a good result in the project were the capacity building webinars and videogames contests held at educational centres, surveys, raffles or prizes during some market days, and the recording of a videodocumentary that also reflected the challenges that Circular Economy poses at local and regional level.

Community based activities also reflect the important role that governance plays in Circular economy, accompanied by adequate policies, as local decision makers and public servants are close to their communities and can encourage citizens and market vendors to participate in the activities, while they also may be limited by the competencies in waste management policies (i.e. existence of higher level regulations, local budget or logistics such as containers). On their part, civil society organisations reveal as key stakeholders, as their participation encourage other citizens to adopt circular strategies such as reducing waste, or using biodegradable). **Collaboration of the Quadruple Helix is considered essential for the long-term sustainability of the initiatives,** providing with knowledge, skills and resources (i.e. funding) to engage communities in the implementation. The initiative could be expanded to other types of wastes such as textile, electronic waste, to provide educational material on resource use and alternatives, and promote circular business models such as reuse or refurbish. It could also be replicated in other municipalities, as knowledge transfer, and activities like raffles or prizes do not require

complex technologies, although they are highly time-demanding; on the contrary, activities that need technologically advanced processes (such as the upcycling of fruit and vegetable waste) are more difficult to replicate as they have strong dependency on waste volume and characteristics, and external funding.

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9 ANNEXES

9.1.1 Communication materials

Figure 27. Roll Up for community-based scheme

Figure 28. Poster for community-based scheme

Figure 29. A2C flyer in Spanish

Figure 30. Design of the booth installed in the street market

¿Quieres llevarte a casa una cesta de alimentos locales y de temporada?

¡GRATIS PARA TI!

¿Participa en nuestro sorteo y gana la tuya!

¡Rellena esta encuesta y llévala al Puesto 1, Avda. de Juan Carlos I

GANA 20KG DE FRUTA Y VERDURA DE TEMPORADA

NOMBRE:
Nº DE TELÉFONO:

Acepto participar en el sorteo y proporcionar mis datos con fines de comunicación al ganador del sorteo.

1 SEÑALA LA DEFINICIÓN MÁS ADECUADA DE ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR:

La economía circular es un modelo de producción y consumo que implica compartir, alquilar, reutilizar, reparar, renovar y reciclar materiales y productos existentes todas las veces que sea posible para crear valor añadido.

Se trata de un modelo basado en producir, consumir y reciclar.

2 ¿RECICLAS DE FORMA HABITUAL?

Sí Casi Siempre A veces No

3 ¿RECICLA EN ALGUNO DE ESTOS CENTROS?

En casa En el trabajo Otros

4 ¿SABÍAS QUE CON LOS RESIDUOS DE FRUTA Y VERDURA DE ESTE MERCADILLO SE PUEDE HACER:

Productos nutricionales Cosméticos Zumo y mermeladas Todo lo anterior

5 ¿SABÍAS QUE CON LA ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR:

Cuidas y respetas al planeta Es motor de empleo e innovación Puedes generar nuevas materias todas las materias

Figure 32. Brochure and survey used in the raffle

BASES LEGALES DEL SORTEO

PARA PARTICIPAR EN EL SORTEO DE HOY HAY QUE CUMPLIMENTAR UNA ENCUESTA Y DEPOSITARLA EN UNA URNA UBICADA EN LA CARPA DE LA FUNDACIÓN PRIMAFRIO EL PUESTO N°1 DEL MERCADILLO DE ALHAMA DE MURCIA, ENTRE LAS 09:00 AM Y 13:00 PM. (FUERA DE ESTE HORARIO NO SE ADMITIRÁN NINGUNA ENCUESTA)

SÓLO SE PERMITIRÁ PARTICIPAR A UNA PERSONA POR ENCUESTA CUMPLIMENTADA EN EL SORTEO Y DEPOSITADA.

EL PREMIO ES UNA CESTA* O LOTE DE FRUTA Y VERDURA CON UN TOTAL DE 20 KG, ENTRE TODOS LOS PRODUCTOS.

EL SORTEO TENDRÁ LUGAR HOY MISMO A LAS 13:00 ENTRE LAS HOJAS DEPOSITADAS EN LA URNA UBICADA EN LA CARPA DE LA FUNDACIÓN PRIMAFRIO, DESTINADA A TAL FIN. (NO SE ADMITIRÁN ENCUESTA QUE FALTE ALGÚN CAMPO O NO ESTÉ IDENTIFICADA PARA SU COMUNICACIÓN)

LA DIRECCIÓN POR CAUSAS AJENAS SE RESERVA DE PROPORCIONAR UNA CESTA U OTRO RECIPIENTE SIMILAR.

LOS DATOS RECOGIDOS EN LA ENCUESTA SE TRATARÁN DE FORMA ANÓNIMA. LOS DATOS PERSONALES SERÁN UTILIZADOS ÚNICAMENTE PARA CONTACTAR CON EL GANADOR.

Figure 31. Poster with legal conditions of the raffle

Figure 33. Photo of A2C materials disposed of at the booth.

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